

similar ring-closure in IV ($R=CN$) was investigated. The condensation of ethyl *iso*-propyl cyanacetate and the chloride of 7-methoxycoumarin-6-carboxylic acid was carried out as described in the case of *isopropyl* malonic ester derivative with the difference that the temperature was maintained at 130° . The residue from toluene was crystallised from alcohol and had m.p. 156° . [Found : C, 64.25 ; H, 5.37 ; N, 3.98. $C_{15}H_{13}O_6N$ (IV, $R=CN$) requires C, 63.86 ; H, 5.32 ; N, 3.92 per cent]. The substance (1 g.) in sulphuric acid (5 c.c.), left for 12 hours at room temperature and then for 2 hours at $40-50^{\circ}$ gave a substance after decomposition with ice which crystallised from hot benzene and had m.p. $258-60^{\circ}$. (Found : C, 59.79 ; H, 3.99 per cent). This substance is not the coumaranone derivative expected. It degraded to 7-methoxycoumarin-6-carboxylic acid when treated with ammoniacal silver nitrate.

Reaction of the Chloride of 7-Methoxycoumarin-6-carboxylic Acid with isoButyl Zinc iodide.—The acid chloride (6 g.) suspended in dry toluene (10 g.) was treated with *iso*-butyl zinc iodide (prepared from 15 g. of *isobutyl* iodide) in toluene. After standing in ice for 2 hours and then at room temperature (30°) for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours, the mixture was decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid. The residue from toluene was washed free from 7-methoxycoumarin-6-carboxylic acid with sodium bicarbonate solution and was treated with ether. The ethereal solution furnished a product which after crystallisation from petroleum ether had m.p. $87-89^{\circ}$. (Found : C, 65.49 ; H, 6.2. $C_{15}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 65.21 ; H, 5.8 per cent). A mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of *isobutyl* ester of 7-methoxycoumarin-6-carboxylic acid (m.p. $99-101^{\circ}$) was $87-90^{\circ}$.

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EXPERIMENTS ON THE SYNTHESIS OF OREOSELONE. PART II.

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ω -Chlororesacetophenone condenses with ethyl acetoacetate to give 6-chloroacetyl-7-hydroxycoumarin which is transformed to the related furanocoumarin. But alkylation of this substance proved difficult. It, however, condenses with acetone to give a monomolecular condensation product. ω -Chlororesacetophenone also condenses with oxaloacetic ester and the product has been converted into the related furanocoumarin and condensed with acetone.

Clayton (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 2016) found that a nitro, carboxyl, carboethoxyl and acetyl group in the *meta* position of a phenol molecule prevented Pechmann reaction taking place with a β -ketonic ester although Shah, Sethna, Bannerjee and Chakravarti (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 714) found that β -methyl resorcylic acid condensed with ethyl acetoacetate. It has been found that β -resorcylic acid condensed with malic acid (Part I, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23365) to give simultaneously a 7-hydroxy- and a 5-hydroxycoumarin derivative. It has now been found that ω -chlororesacetophenone condenses with ethyl acetoacetate to give (I, $R=Me$) in poor yield. The condensation

takes place in presence of both sulphuric acid and alcoholic hydrogen chloride. The substance (I, R=Me) can be converted difficultly into coumaranone (II, R=Me; R₁=H) in dioxane solution. But the introduction of *isopropyl* group in (II, R₁=H; R=Me) is not possible on account of the ease with which its sodio derivative decomposes. The substance (II, R₁=H; R=Me), however, condenses with acetone to give (III, R=Me). Shriver and Anderson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **60**, 1416) found 6-methoxycoumaranone to condense with acetone unimolecularly; but under the conditions described in Part I, a bimolecular condensation product is obtained. However, in the present case, the condensation takes place under the conditions described in experimental sequel. But the catalytic reduction of (III, R=Me) to the substance (II, R₁=CHMe₂; R=Me) proved difficult. This scheme for the synthesis of oreoselone, which seemed so promising from the above model experiment, failed because ω -chlororesacetophenone does not react either with malic acid, hydroxymethylene acetic ester, ethoxymethylene acetic ester or acetoxymethylene acetic ester. But it has been found that ω -chlororesacetophenone condenses with oxaloacetic ester to give (I, R=CO₂Et) but with great difficulty. This result is reminiscent of the exceptional behaviour of oxaloacetic ester towards quinol with which other β -ketonic esters show little tendency to react.

The ring-closure of the substance (I, R=CO₂Et) to (II, R₁=H; R=CO₂Et) proves to be extremely difficult, all methods based on the use of sodium acetate in various solvents such as ethyl alcohol, dioxane, glycerin, phenol, pyridine, dimethylaniline fail. But ice-cold ammonia (*d*, 0.88) under carefully controlled condition brings about the desired transformation. The substance (II, R=CO₂Et; R₁=H) condenses with acetone to give (III, R=CO₂Et). Hydrolysis, catalytic reduction and decarboxylation of (III, R=CO₂Et) will lead to oreoselone.

EXPERIMENTAL

4. Methyl-6-chloroaceto-7-hydroxycoumarin.—A mixture of ω -chlororesacetophenone (4 g.), ethyl acetoacetate (3 c.c.), absolute alcohol (35 c.c.) was saturated with dry hydrogen chloride in the ice-cold and left overnight in a flask tightly corked. Next morning, half the alcohol was removed by distillation and the residue poured over crushed ice. The pasty mass after treatment with ether became solid and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 235-36°, yield 0.2 g. To a mixture of ω -chlororesacetophenone (4 g.), ethyl acetoacetate (4 g.), concentrated sulphuric acid (8 c.c.) was added in the ice-cold. The mixture was allowed to stand at 20-25° for 48 hours and then poured on to ice. The product isolated as before had m.p. 235-36°, yield 0.5g. (Found: C, 57.56; H, 3.55. C₁₂H₉O₄Cl requires C, 57.3; H, 3.95 per cent).

Preparation of (II, R=Me; R₁=H).—The foregoing substance (3.0 g.), dissolved in dioxane (60 c.c.) was mixed with powdered sodium acetate (15 g.) and heated on the steam-bath for 2 hours and finally gently refluxed for 15 minutes. After cooling, the mixture

was diluted with water and the precipitated solids crystallised from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether, m.p. 267-68° (decomp.), yield 1 g. (Found : C, 66.78 ; H, 4.14. $C_{12}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 66.66 ; H, 3.7 per cent). Attempts at isopropylation of the above compound in various solvents such as anisole, decalin, etc., with sodamide and isopropyl iodide failed. But it readily condensed with piperonal (piperidine condensing agent) to give a *piperonylidene* derivative, m. p. 290° (acetic acid). (Found : C, 69.12 ; H, 3.58. $C_{20}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 68.96 ; H, 3.45 per cent.) showing the presence of $COCH_2$ grouping. The *coumaranone* (0.7 g.) dissolved in pure dimethylaniline (30 g.) was mixed with pure dry acetone (4 c.c.) and piperidine (3 drops). The mixture was heated at 120° for 2 hours and then at 150° for 2 hours. After the recovery of dimethylaniline by steam distillation, the residue was boiled with hydrochloric acid and filtered. The insoluble portion was crystallised from xylene-petroleum ether and had m.p. 232°. [Found : C, 70.44 ; H, 4.99. $C_{13}H_{12}O_4$ (III, R=Me) requires C, 70.31 ; H, 4.66 per cent].

β-Carboethoxy-6-chloroaceto-7-hydroxycoumarin (I, R=CO₂Et).—*ω*-Chlororesacetophenone did not condense with oxaloacetic ester in presence of sulphuric acid or phosphorous pentoxide. The condensation can be brought about as follows : *ω*-Chlororesacetophenone (4 g.), oxaloacetic ester (5 c.c.) and zinc chloride (well powdered, 4 g.) were well mixed and to this dry alcohol (40 c.c.) was added. The solution was then saturated with hydrogen chloride and the characteristic greenish fluorescence of an umbelliferone derivative appeared in 1 hour which ultimately became greenish black. After standing at the room temperature (20-25°) for 48 hours the separated product (A) was collected and the filtrate left for 4 days. After collecting the deposit (B), the filtrate was poured on to ice and the semi-solid mass extracted with ether. The residue (C) from ether was mixed with (A) and (B). The mixed solids were crystallised from carbon tetrachloride and also from benzene-ligroin, yield 3 g. (Found : C, 53.98 ; H, 4.01. $C_{14}H_{11}O_4Cl$ requires C, 54.1 ; H, 3.55 per cent).

The ring-closure of the substance (I, R=CO₂Et) to (II, R₁=H ; R=CO₂Et) proved to be extremely difficult. The chloro-ketone (1 g.) was ground with chilled (to 0°) liquor ammonia and the yellow solution left aside at the room temperature for 10-15 minutes when it turned dark red. It was then warmed on the steam-bath at 50-60° for 10 minutes. The solution was again well cooled and neutralised with hydrochloric acid below 5°. The greenish precipitate was well washed, collected, dried and finally crystallised from benzene-ligroin mixture, m.p. 179-81°, yield 0.6 g. The greenish colour of the crude product is due to a complex impurity which is eliminated during crystallisation. (Found : C, 61.4 ; H, 3.75. $C_{14}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 61.3 ; H, 3.65 per cent). The substance was nitrogen free and non-acidic.

The coumaranone (II, R=CO₂Et ; R₁=H) (0.7 g.), dissolved in pure dimethylaniline (30 c.c.), was mixed with acetone (3 c.c.) and piperidine (3 drops) and heated at 120° (2-3 hours) and at 150° (2 hours). The product, isolated as previously, crystallised from dilute methanol and also from a mixture of acetone and carbon tetrachloride, m. p. 264-66° (decomp.). [Found : C, 65.22 ; H, 5.15. $C_{17}H_{14}O_6$ (III, R=CO₂Et) requires C, 65.0 ; H, 4.45 per cent].